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RURAL ENERGY PROBLEMS: SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN INDIA

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Abstract:

India is both a major energy producer and a consumer in the globe. India currently, as the world's seventh largest energy producer, accounting for about 2.49 per cent of the world's total annual energy production. It is also the world's fifth largest energy consumer, accounting for about 3.45 per cent of the world's total annual energy consumption in 2004. Since independence, the country has been significant expansion in the total energy use in the country with a shift from non-commercial to commercial sources. The share of commercial energy in total primary energy consumption rose from 59.7 per cent in 1980-81 to 72.6 per cent in 2006-07. It must be noted, however, that India's per capita energy consumption is one of the lowest in the world. India consumed 455 kgoe per person of primary energy in 2004, which is around 26 per cent of world average of 1750 kgoe in that year. As compared to this, per capita energy consumption in China and Brazil was 1147 kgoe and 1232kgoe, respectively (**GOI-2007-2012**). Universal energy access to modern energy services is essential for socio-economic development including poverty alleviation. However, globally over 1200 million people lack access to affordable basic energy services, such as effective lighting and clean cooking. India alone is home to over 300 million people deprived of electricity and more than 800 million people who depend on solid biomass as fuel for cooking. Hence, there is a growing focus on energy poverty which implies lack of access to modern energy services. These services are defined as household's access to electricity and clean cooking solutions, such as fuels and improved cook stoves that are not detrimental to health and the environment (IEA 2013). The amount of energy needed to satisfy the basic needs of rural populations around the world is relatively small, and appropriate technologies are available however, widening access to modern energy services is limited by the extreme poverty found particularly in the least developed countries. Living standards in rural areas can be significantly improved by promoting a shift from direct combustion of biomass fuels (dung, crop

residues, and fuel wood) or coal in inefficient and polluting stoves to clean, efficient liquid or gaseous fuels and electricity. Although consumers trend to shift to these modern, higher-quality energy carriers as their incomes rise and the carriers become more affordable, the process is slow. Shift to such carriers can reduce the damage to human health and the drudgery associated with continued reliance on inefficient, polluting solid fuels. Technological developments alone, however, will not improve access or promote greater equity. New institutional measures are also needed, including financing to cover the initial capital costs of devices and equipment. Energy initiatives will be most successful when integrated with other policies that promote development. And because local populations will ultimately use, maintain, and pay for energy services, they should be involved in making decisions about energy systems. The lack of adequate energy services in rural areas of developing countries has social dimensions as well as serious environmental and health effects. Many of these problems are exacerbated by the almost exclusive reliance of rural populations in most areas on traditional fuels coupled with simple technologies characterized by low energy efficiency and harmful emissions. This paper attempted to focus on technological opportunities, as well as other strategies, for delivering adequate, affordable, rural energy problems. Besides, several policies and fiscal measures along with implementing wide range of programmes on renewables, have contributed a significant progress and achievement made on the renewable energy. Further, in this background of the paper attempt to list the programmes on renewables and examine their impact on energy economy of India. At the end, this paper highlights the need for sustainable strategies and policies for renewables in order to meet the needs of the present as well as the future generation.

Introduction

Economic growth, the world over is driven by energy, whether in the form of finite resources such as coal, oil and gas or renewable such as hydroelectric, wind, solar and biomass energy. Energy generation and consumption powers the nation's industries, vehicles, homes and offices. Energy also has significant impact on the quality of a country's air, water, land and forest resources. For future growth to be both rapid and sustainable, a nation needs to be as resource efficient and environmentally benign as possible. Many people in the developing world lack access to energy sources such as oil, gas, and electricity, and still depend on biomass. The

problems of supplying them with modern fuels appear daunting, but practical and financially sustainable solutions exist. Energy markets do not function efficiently in many developing countries, particularly in rural areas, where nearly 2 billion people do not have electricity or access to modern fuels such as oil and gas. The problem is likely to worsen in coming decades. The population of the developing world is expected to increase by 3 billion over the next forty years, and energy demand per capita will grow rapidly. As countries economic development proceeds, their per capita consumption of commercial energy increases. Per capita consumption of commercial energy in the United States, for example, is 80 times higher than in Africa, 40 times higher than in South Asia, 15 times higher than in East Asia, and 8 times higher than in Latin America. Inadequate energy markets threaten to reduce economic growth, walk with difficulty development, and keep living standards low. Although grid electrification is the traditional means of providing reliable electricity supplies, connection to distant grids will be too expensive to be cost effective for many rural areas. Fortunately, there are a number of promising alternatives for increasing energy supplies even in very remote areas, ranging from more efficient use of traditional fuels to advanced technologies based on renewable energy sources. Population growth, the number of households without electricity is still large and is even growing in some regions. One-third of all energy consumed in the developing world comes from biomass. In addition to being their primary source of energy, biomass also provides many people in the developing world with a livelihood. According to some estimates, smoke contributes to acute respiratory infections that affect 4 million infants and children a year. Studies have shown that nonsmoking women in India and Nepal who have cooked on biomass stoves for many years have a higher-than-normal incidence of chronic respiratory disease. The use of wood fuels has also taken a serious toll on the environment in many regions, leading to deforestation, soil erosion, and reduced soil fertility. Deforestation, in turn, has forced many poor people to resort to even less efficient sources of energy, such as crop residues and dung materials that could otherwise have been used for fertilizer. Finally, many children and adults in developing countries must spend up to several hours per day gathering fuel; this leaves them less time for schooling and productive activities and thus perpetuates poverty.

Renewable Energy in Rural India

According to IEA, primary energy demand in developing Asia is expected to grow from 3.2 btoe in 2006 to 6.3 btoe in 2030. This growth is not sustainable if most of this energy has to be met by fossil fuels. Higher fossil fuel consumption will significantly increase greenhouse gas emissions. It is widely known that global warming is caused by greenhouse gas emissions, largely from the heavy use of fossil fuels. Significant changes in climate are being observed, some of which may have serious consequences worldwide. Many economies have adopted policies to reduce their projected energy demand. However, much more needs to be done to reverse the current trend of increasing greenhouse gas emissions. India is facing a serious problem of adequate energy supply. Condition of energy supply in rural India is even more serious. According to GoI only 37 percent of rural households had electricity connections in 1997. As per census 2001, only 43 percent of rural population has electricity. Providing electricity to all rural people is still a challenge for the nation, and it is very difficult to cover all villages under electric grid due to their remote geographical locations. As per Census of India 2001, 43.6 per cent of the rural households were dependent on electricity as energy source for lighting; this number has increased to 55.3 per cent, as reported in Census of India 2011. In urban India, electricity remains as the primary energy source for lighting in majority of households for each of the above census periods. It is argued in this paper that the best way to solve this problem is to make use of renewable energy sources especially in remote villages. Many efforts have been made in this direction to meet this challenge but could not achieve targets. Still India has ample potential of renewable energy, which is required to be exploited. India ranks sixth in the world in terms of energy demand accounting for 3.5 percent of world's commercial energy demand in 2001. With a gross domestic product growth of 8 per cent set for the 10th Five Year Plan, the energy demand is expected to grow at 5.2 per cent. Although, commercial energy consumption has grown rapidly over the last two decades, a large part of India's population does not have access to it. Per capita energy consumption is also low even compared to some of the developing countries. Primarily commercial energy demand grows almost three fold at an annual rate of 6.0 per cent between 1981 and 2001 to reach 314.7 Mtoe. India's incremental energy demand for the next decade is projected to be among the highest in the world. India's commercial energy demand is expected to grow even more rapidly than in the past as it goes down the reforms path in order to raise standards of living.

Trends in primary energy demand and supply

The demand for energy, particularly for commercial energy, has been growing rapidly with the growth of the economy, changes in the demographic structure, rising urbanization, socio economic development, and the desire for attaining and sustaining self-reliance in some sectors of the economy.

Table 1: Trends in Demand and Supply of Primary Energy (All in Mtoe)[#]

	1960-61	1970-71	1980-81	1990-91	2000-01	2006-07	2011-12
Domestic Production of Commercial Energy	36.78	47.67	75.19	150.01	207.08	259.56	435
Net Imports	6.04	12.66	24.63	31.07	89.03	131.97	111
Total Commercial Energy	42.82	60.33	99.82	181.08	296.11	391.53	546
Non-Commercial Energy	74.38	86.72	108.48	122.07	136.64	147.56	169
Total Primary Energy Demand	117.20	147.05	208.30	303.15	432.75	539.09	715

Source: IEPR [#] Mtoe = Million tonne of oil equivalent

Table 2 : Energy consumption: Source Wise

Energy Source	1960-61	1970-71	1980-81	1990-91	2000-01	2006-07	2011-12
Coal	35.64	36.48	56.96	94.15	131.52	200.02	270
Lignite	0.01	0.81	1.23	3.58	6.43	8.72	13
Oil	8.29	19.14	32.26	57.75	106.97	132.75	186
Natural gas	-	0.06	1.41	11.49	25.07	34.60	48
Hydro power	0.67	2.17	4.00	6.16	6.40	9.75	12
Nuclear power	-	0.63	0.78	1.60	4.41	4.86	17
Wind Power	-	-	-	-	0.13	0.83	< 1
Total	44.61	59.83	96.73	174.73	280.93	391.53	546

Source: Planning Commission

Non commercial energy resources include the traditional fuels such as wood, cow dung, crop residue, and biogas and constitute a significant percentage of total primary energy consumption in the country. A larger share of these fuels is used by the households, particularly in rural areas, for meeting their cooking and heating needs. The consumption of 147.56 mtoe of

traditional fuels in 2006-07 includes consumption of 238 Mt of fuel wood, 98 Mt of dung and 38 Mt of agriculture waste. Around 80 per cent of the fuel wood is used for household consumption and the balance is used by the cottage industry, hotels, etc. According to GoI 2011, 55.3 per cent of rural households and 92.7 per cent of urban households, respectively, depend on electricity as primary energy source for lighting; Further 86.7 per cent of rural households and 26.3 per cent of urban households depend on solid biomass as primary energy source for cooking.

Rural Energy Problems and Challenges

India's population (65.0 per cent) is rural-based. According to GoI around 20,000 villages have never seen electricity which means almost 40-60 million people are still living in Stone Age. Even the other so called electrified villages get only 3-4 hours of electricity every day which is as good as having no electricity. This is a sad state of affairs even 61 years after independence. No electricity and primitive cookstoves. Around 300,000 deaths in year take place because of pollution. 54.0 per cent of India's population is below 25 years and most of them live in rural areas with very little employment opportunities. 1/4th of our population or 260 million live on less than \$1 per day. Because of rural poverty large scale migration to cities takes place leading to serious urban problems. Energy is the basis of life. Lack of it produces economic stagnation and social upheavals. Serious energy crisis in India, Per capita electricity in India 553 kwh per year or 4.0 per cent that in US and lowest in the global. In rural households 57 kwh per year, per capita electricity consumption. The 8.0 per cent to 9.0 per cent per annum growth in petroleum/oil consumption in India and China's Oil consumption at present rate will create world wide crisis and need for alternatives. In poor countries with annual per capita incomes of \$300 or less, at least 90.0 per cent of the population depends on wood and dung for cooking. But people move up the "energy ladder" as their incomes grow, eventually switching to electricity for lighting and fossil fuels for cooking; in agriculture and industry, diesel engines and electricity replace manual and animal power. The transition to modern fuels is usually complete by the time annual per capita incomes reach \$1,000 – \$1,500. With technological progress and reductions in the costs of modern fuels, the income level at which people make the transition can decline significantly. Because biomass use will continue throughout the developing world for some time

to come, energy policies must support ways to use wood fuels more efficiently and sustainably, while creating the necessary conditions for supplying modern fuels to those who lack them.

Farm forestry: Planting trees, shrubs, and grasses on farmlands and between crops and forest management have long played an important role in alleviating wood shortages in China, India, and many other countries. Because farmers outnumber foresters in most countries by several thousand to one, involving them in planting trees and shrubs can dramatically accelerate afforestation. And the incentive to participate in farm forestry programs is strong: wood fetches a high price in some urban markets, and trees and shrubs can supply farmers with fodder, building materials, green mulch, fruit, and other by products that may be as valuable as the firewood itself. Experience suggests that effective management of existing forest resources depends on letting local people take responsibility for forests or woodlands. Some successful participatory effects have now been pioneered in several countries. In these programs, farmers get to sell all the wood extracted from local woodlands; however, they must participate in a resource-management program developed in collaboration with the national forestry department.

Efficient use of biomass: One way to improve wood fuel use is for governments to encourage the private sector to develop and market improved stoves in rural areas by supporting stove design and testing, and conducting publicity campaigns and training programs. Although fuels from biomass are generally much less efficient for cooking than modern fuels, biogas derived from digesters of dung and farm residues is an exception. Both China and India have done much to develop biogas and encourage its use. However, only farmers who raise livestock can easily acquire biogas; it is thus a cost-effective option for less than 10 percent of most rural populations.

Rural Electrification: Rural demand for electricity comes mainly from households that use electricity for lighting and from farms, agro-industries, and small commercial and manufacturing establishments, which use electricity for productive purposes such as irrigation pumping, water supplies, crop processing, refrigeration, and motive power. Most rural electrification programs have focused on connecting rural areas to national or local grids. However, grid-supplied electricity is not the lowest cost alternative under all conditions. For example, technologies involving wind power, solar thermal power (sunlight used to heat air or water), photovoltaic (PV) cells (which produce electricity directly from sunlight), and small-scale hydropower merit

more attention from policymakers. They are often an ideal way to get energy to rural areas and have significant environmental advantages relative to fossil fuels. Solar power is a particularly attractive option for countries with abundant sunlight and a poorly developed rural grid electrification system. The costs associated with these technologies, once prohibitive, have decreased significantly over the past decade. Today, PV systems supply electricity economically to rural areas throughout the developing world for lighting in homes and schools, domestic appliances, refrigeration in health clinics, village water pumps, telephones, and street lighting.

Energy and Environment

Poor people and people in marginal areas, presently depend on natural resources to provide energy for cooking and heating. By 2030, the number of people in this category is expected to rise from 2.4 billion to 2.6 billion. The result will be greater local competition for traditional energy. The environmental and social impacts of biofuel production, which continues to grow throughout the world, vary depending on the context. Substitution of biofuels for fossil fuels will have positive impacts, primarily in relation to reduction of greenhouse gases and possible recultivation of degraded areas. As a cash crop, biofuels also represent a new source of agricultural income. But there are many questions about the extent to which smallholders will be able to profit from this new market. At the same time, there is a great risk that cultivation to produce biofuels will accelerate soil degradation, over exploitation of water, and loss of biodiversity, and also compete with food production, thereby endangering food security. Global climate change, caused by the burning of fossil fuels, has many adverse ecological impacts on people's livelihood. One study has shown, for example, that 11.0 per cent of the arable land in developing countries will be lost and that cereal production in 65 developing countries will diminish dramatically. Growing demand for energy will exert increased pressure on natural resources in future, thereby posing a threat to the multiple services provided by ecosystems. Should these services be further degraded, poor populations in rural areas who are directly dependent on natural resources.

Energy and Social Development

Almost 1.6 billion people in developing countries have no access to electricity. Approximately 85.0 per cent of these people live in rural areas. Current projections indicate that this number will decline by only 100 million by 2015. 2.5 million People particularly women and children, still die annually of diseases of the airways, because traditional fuels impair the quality of the air in their homes. Electric light, modern means of communication, and access to new media enhances opportunities for education. Cooking and heating with modern sources of fuel or electricity improves health and reduces workloads, above all for women and children. These examples illustrate how modern energy can significantly improve living conditions and hence help to reduce rural exodus. Access to energy services is an important instrument for empowering poor people and disadvantaged population groups and thus for fostering equity. Accordingly, calls to designate access to sustainable energy as a human right are growing louder. If energy production does not keep pace with growing demand, there will be an increased risk that poor people, particularly in rural areas, will find it even more difficult to gain access to electricity and modern fuels.

Energy and Economic Development

The increase in the global market price of fossil fuels is a burden not only on individual household budgets; it is above all a burden on the budgets of many developing countries, amounting to as much as 10-30 per cent of their Gross Domestic Product. The economic and social impacts harbour a potential for conflict that should not be underestimated. Moreover, higher fossil fuel prices diminish the financial options for promoting future-oriented energy projects in rural areas. Sparse settlement and long distances make energy in rural areas more expensive. This imposes economic limits on the concept of central power plants that guarantee a countrywide energy supply through a national grid. Access to modern energy enables agricultural development and the development of productive economic sectors in rural areas. Agricultural products can be processed and sold at higher prices in urban centres, a key factor for poverty alleviation. Rural households thus benefit from value added. Additionally, if people are connected to the national grid, they can benefit from rates that are frequently subsidized. The feasibility of financing rural energy supply, and the financial sustainability of doing so, are closely linked with the potential to promote economic productivity that also benefits poor population groups.

Sustainable Development with regard to Energy

Energy systems are to be consistent with i) environmental, ii) economic and iii) social sustainability aspects to be conducive to sustainable development of a region. The *Environmental Sustainability* includes criteria's such as the pollutants related to energy should not exceed the absorptive capacity of environmental media (land, water and air), etc. *Economic Sustainability* includes aspects such as user costs of energy to be considered in determining the economic feasibility of projects. *Social Sustainability* includes aspects such as the development and use of energy should not harm people's health nor involve involuntary resettlement. The energy projects are required to contribute to poverty alleviation and social equity.

Criteria of Sustainability

- ✓ Energy sources, which satisfy basic human needs
- ✓ Increased energy efficiency and energy conservation
- ✓ Growing awareness about newer energy technologies
- ✓ Reduced forest exploitation
- ✓ Energy from waste
- ✓ Use of locally available bio-manure in agriculture sector and thereby reduced chemical use
- ✓ Integrated, decentralized energy system approach
- ✓ Reduction in pollution
- ✓ Clean and healthy lifestyle
- ✓ Energy system which ensures long term economic, social and environmental health of a region over generations
- ✓ People's participation.

National Energy Policies

The process by which energy services are distributed equitably and produced in an environmentally friendly way requires deliberate political commitment and guidance. This makes it important to take account of the aims of MDGs in national energy policy, rather than giving primary emphasis to maximization of profits. Comprehensive regional and land development planning can serve as the basis for establishing priorities. The following elements support this process:

- ✓ Including all stakeholders, particularly disadvantaged groups, in development of national energy policies. This makes it possible to assess the long-term energy needs of industry, agriculture, the transport sector, rural and urban households, etc. Joint negotiation of goals and priorities will help ensure ownership of the policies developed.
- ✓ Creating legal, institutional and political conditions that promote renewable energy and favour efficiency measures. This includes, for example, the presence of independent authorities to monitor liberalization processes, standardization and quality control, regulatory models for granting concessions, etc.
- ✓ Promoting public-private partnerships that protect also the interests of consumers and allow value added to be channelled to the local population. When PPPs are advantageous for local investors or for alternative models of ownership and operation such as user associations, foreign exchange risk can be reduced and legal validity enhanced.
- ✓ Establishing financing mechanisms and tax measures that make energy services affordable, even for poor population groups. Reducing subsidies for fossil fuels and internalizing external costs helps to promote energy efficiency and renewable energy.
- ✓ Initiating regional cooperation to harmonies infrastructures and encourage exchange of information between neighboring countries, in order to increase energy reliability and efficiency. In addition to technical competence, it will be important above all to strengthen institutional, legal, and scientific competence at the national level, in order to develop and implement these elements.

Ministry of New and Renewable Energy

Ministry of New and Renewable Energy (MNRE) is a ministry of Government of India. The ministry is headed by Farooq Abdullah, a Cabinet Minister. The ministry was established as

the Ministry of Non-Conventional Energy Sources in 1992. It adopted its current name in October 2006. The Ministry is mainly responsible for research and development, intellectual property protection, and international cooperation, promotion, and coordination in renewable energy sources such as wind power, small hydro, biogas, and solar power. The broad aim of the Ministry is to develop and deploy new and renewable energy for supplementing the energy requirements of India.

The mission of the Ministry is to bring in Energy Security; Increase the share of clean power; increase Energy Availability and Access; improve Energy Affordability; and maximize Energy Equity.

The major functional area or Allocation of Business of MNRE is

- Commission for Additional Sources of Energy (CASE);
- Indian Renewable Energy Development Agency (IREDA);
- Integrated Rural Energy Programme (IREP);
- Research and development of Biogas and programmes relating to Biogas units;
- Solar Energy including Solar Photovoltaic devices and their development, production and applications;
- Programme relating to improved chulhas and research and development thereof;
- All matters relating to small/mini/micro hydel projects of and below 25 MW capacities;
- Research and development of other non-conventional/renewable sources of energy and programmes relating thereto;
- Tidal energy; and
- Geothermal Energy;

Biofuel: (i) National Policy; (ii) research, development and demonstration on transport, stationary and other applications; (iii) setting up of a National Bio-fuels Development Board and strengthening the existing institutional mechanism; and (iv) overall coordination.

Major Energy Programmes

- Jawaharlal Nehru National Solar Mission (JNNSM) - The objective of the mission is to establish India as a global leader in solar energy, by creating the policy conditions for its diffusion across the country as quickly as possible.
- National Biogas and Manure Management Programme (NBMMP)
- Solar Lantern Programme
- Solar thermal energy Demonstration Programme
- Remote Village Lighting Programme
- National Biomass Cookstoves Initiative (NBCI)

Conclusion

India faces an enormous challenge in meeting its energy requirement over the coming 25 years to support a growth rate of Eight percent. This challenge can be met with a coherent approach which develops all her energy resources. The main areas action for which detailed policy recommendations are made as follows:

- i. Promoting energy efficiency and conservation
- ii. Enhancing energy security
- iii. Encouraging renewables and local solutions
- iv. Promoting and focusing energy R&D
- v. Promoting energy security through entitlements for the poor, gender equity and empowerment
- vi. Creating an enabling environment and regulatory oversight for competitive efficiency.

To integrated approach in energy planning through decentralized planning machinery it is possible to achieve the goal of sustainability. Education, awareness, people's participation, economic benefits plays a vital role in the adoption of environmentally sound energy technologies. Currently growth of renewable, non-conventional energy technologies is limited only to biogas. In fact the region has potentiality to many other energy technologies like solar, wind, etc which are not in developmental stage mainly because of economic constraints. Rural areas gain access to energy is a great challenge, but the means available for realizing this goal have expanded considerably in recent years. As renewable energy systems come down in cost, they are becoming an increasingly attractive way to provide electricity to rural areas. The costs

of grid electrification schemes can also be reduced to make electricity more affordable to a broader spectrum of rural people, and new, off-grid rural companies and cooperatives can emerge if competition is promoted, barriers to entry are reduced, and the pricing playing field is leveled. Moreover, continued use of biomass need not deplete the environment, thanks to farm-forestry and forest management programs that involve farmers. Concerted efforts by governments, policymakers, the private sector, and NGOs, coupled with significant local participation, can lead to impressive results.

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